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Confluence of Research, Theory and Practice in the
Built Environment

EDITORS

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EXPLORING THE DIVERSIFICATION LEVEL OF QUANTITY SURVEYING FIRMS IN SOUTH WEST NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The crisis in the country's economy has caused some firms in the construction industry to fail in terms of meeting their required expectation. This is evident in the way firms are striving to survive and continuously look out for other businesses outside their core business or area of specialization. In Nigerian "construction industry", organisation such as the quantity surveying firms are not exempted. These firms need to understand and decide on a suitable business into. Hence, the research explored the level of diversification of quantity surveying firms in south west Nigeria, Oyo and Lagos States as a case study. A quantitative design was adopted and the questionnaire was used to gather information from eighty-two (82) quantity surveying (QS) firms in the study area. The questionnaires were distributed to all 82 QS firms using a census survey, though fifty-eight (58) representing 67% of responses were retrieved and found suitable for analysis. Descriptive and inferential statistics such as frequency distribution and percentage were used for analyzing the collected data. The research findings showed that the majority of QS firms diversified into other businesses though at a moderate level since about 70% of the revenue generated by the firms is from the dominant business. Hence, this research recommended that quantity surveying firms should diversify into other profitable businesses at a high level without becoming sidetracked from their core profession to enhance sustainability in an unstable economy.

Keywords: business, diversification, economy, quantity surveying firms, sustainability.

INTRODUCTION

As economic globalization advances, it is becoming increasingly challenging for business to forecast their future workloads in the construction industry because of its increasing complexity, volatility and competitiveness (Makarfi *et al.*, 2009; Okereke *et al.*, 2022). Diversifying their competitiveness (Makarfi *et al.*, 2009; Okereke *et al.*, 2022). Rahim *et al.* (2013) submitted that quantity surveying firms are affected by environmental issues such as economic crisis, pandemic, etc, these have caused many firms to fail in meeting their expectation. Other firms strive to survive while quantity surveying firms are not exempted. In

this, quantity surveying firms need alternative businesses for sustainability in the turbulence economy (Okereke *et al.*, 2022).

Diversifying their activities is a growing strategy used by construction companies to stay afloat and competitive. Construction companies grow in the hope that improved performance will result from their expansion, including increased levels of market power, growth facilitation, and profitability (Surya *et al.*, 2021). As a growth strategy, diversification entails exceeding previous performance levels with a notable rise in performance targets, typically sales or market share (Edwards, 2014). According to Rahman (2017), diversification is the process of investing in multiple companies or industries. It is a financial strategy that allows a company to spread its risk so that, if something goes wrong in one industry, it still has options. According to Zinnia and Indrani (2022), businesses frequently diversify to reduce risk by reducing the possibility of harm to the company during national economic downturns. The fundamental notion is to diversify into a new line of business that is not adversely affected by the same economic downturns as the firm's current activity; if a firm experiences market losses, one of the other ventures will assist in offsetting those losses and ensure the firm's continued viability (Purcell, 2022).

Quantity Surveying Firms (QSFs) have had to diversify into different industries to maintain their survival and increase performance (Adamu *et al.*, 2011). QSFs are service-oriented businesses that offer their clients professional counsel, services, and consulting. To meet their clients' demands for value for money, quantity surveying firms primarily rely on the abilities, knowledge, and experience of quantity surveyors (Perera & Anushka, 2016). To thrive and maintain their competitiveness, quantity surveying companies are progressively looking to diversify their business lines (Oyewobi *et al.*, 2013). According to Olanrewaju and Anavhe (2015), quantity surveying is an international field that offers services to a range of sectors. All stages of a facility's life cycle, including feasibility, design, building, extension, refurbishment, maintenance, and demolition, are handled by quantity surveyors. Purcell (2022) argued that a firm can diversify by entering new markets or product categories that are associated with its primary industry. For example, if they have the necessary skills in the field of professions, a quantity surveyor can work as an architect, project manager, real estate agent, Mechanical and Electrical engineering (M&E) consultant, or even contractor on various projects in the building business. As long as businesses can handle each business well, it is also a good way to control risk (Zinnia & Indrani, 2022).

Furthermore, to achieve better performance, firms expand their operations in the hopes of increasing profitability, facilitating growth, and achieving higher levels of market power. A profitable company increases earnings over the long run, creating jobs and raising people's standard of living (Surya *et al.*, 2021). According to Chen *et al.* (2014), managers need to understand the connection between performance and diversification to make decisions that will improve the firm's success. Edwards (2014) noted that most firms fail because they do not diversify from their core business into having more than one core competency, which allows them to fall back on alternative businesses in a turbulence economy. Therefore, this study explores the level of diversification of quantity surveying firms in south west Nigeria, case study of Oyo and Lagos States.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Quantity Surveying Profession

According to Opawole *et al.* (2012), quantity surveying is a multidisciplinary field that focuses on the precise computation and measurement of labor and materials needed for construction projects, such as engineering and building projects. Quantity surveying profession deals with estimating, planning, and controlling the cost of construction projects throughout the life cycle. Feasibility and viability studies, work estimating and quantification, cost planning, procurement and tendering contract control, and construction management are some of the quantity surveying techniques used in building project pricing. Olanrewaju and Anavhe (2015) submitted that quantity surveying practices involves cost management, procurement, and contractual issues in the supply chain and marketplace for construction.

Moreso, Ajanlekoko (2012) discussed quantity surveying as the synthesis of various fields, including construction technology, law, accounting, business management, and information management within the particular framework of the built environment. Quantity surveyors are professionals who have received professional training and experience in handling building expenses, management, and communication (Chandramohan *et al.*, 2022). The quantity surveyor monitors and updates initial estimates and contracts.

Quantity Surveying Firms

A quantity surveying firm is a service-based organization that provides expert advice, services, and consultancy to the client. To be able to meet clients' demands for value for money, quantity surveying firms mostly rely on the abilities, knowledge, and experience of quantity surveyors. Moreover, Perera and Anushka (2016) stated that quantity surveying firms depend on quantity surveyors' services, knowledge, and data to address client's needs and provide expert advice, services, and consultancy.

Diversification of Quantity Surveying Firms

Diversification is a growth strategy that significantly increases performance objectives beyond past performance levels. It is the practice of distributing capital among several companies or sectors to avoid a company having to place all of its eggs in one basket. If something goes wrong in one industry, it can still rely on the other. According to Lioudis (2022), diversification is the practice of distributing capital over several different investments and investment kinds. The rationale for this strategy is that business owners can switch to other ventures if one venture fails. Additionally, Purcell (2022) advised a developing business to diversify its investments across multiple industries and increase its client base by broadening its offering of products and services. Long-term success is probable for businesses with consistent growth.

Oladimeji and Udosen (2019) established that managers have an innate desire to increase the profit and growth potential of their organizations by minimizing reliance on stagnant or decreasing markets by implementing a diversification strategy. According to Zhou (2011), a diversified firm's ability to manage many business divisions contributes to the creation of economies of scope. Nevertheless, Catherine (2021) submitted that diversification is necessary when the investor's gains from the primary business are no longer commensurate with the risk assumed. According to Arslan *et al.* (2023), diversification is one of the primary options that construction companies services to survive.

However, Abidin *et al.* (2010) submitted that quantity surveying firms now offer a wide range of services, such as insurance assessments and taxation advice, among others, as a corrective measure to address the difficulties experienced through a means of diversification. Additionally, Frei *et al.* (2013) argued that a stronger emphasis on sustainability had given QS firms access to new fields such as expert witness services, alternative dispute resolution, and quantification of the environmental impact of different construction activities. QS firms also offer a variety of services to rail networks and the oil and gas sectors (Owusu-Manu *et al.*, 2014). However, quantity surveying profession is expected to grow significantly in the future when diversification of QS firms are taken into consideration.

Level of Firms Diversification

According to Adams (2022), diverse firms differ in terms of how diversified they are. A diversified firm has ownership or involvement in multiple industry sectors. The three levels of diversification that are known to exist are low, moderate, and high as suggested by (Adams, 2022).

Low Level of Diversification

Shaw (2023) submitted that a firm that concentrates its operations primarily on one dominant business tends to have a low level of diversification. If the firm's revenue exceeds 95% of its total sales, it is considered to be in a single business. On the other hand, Lioudis (2022) argued that firms that make revenue from a single product fall under the actual definition of a non-diversified firm. According to Edwards (2014), a low-level diversified firm has very little diversity because its main priorities are its core capabilities and business. Businesses that get more than 95 percent of their revenue from a single business segment are classified as low-level diversified firms by Kabeyi (2018).

Moreover, Dyer *et al.* (2016) argued that low level diversified firms are those that earn above 70% and 95% of their revenue from their primary business line and the remaining portion from business situated in the values chain with either forward or backward integration. These firms derive more than 70% of their revenue from their primary business line and the remaining portion from other lines across different value chains, as opposed to dominant vertical businesses that are from the same value chain.

Moderate Level of Diversification

For moderate to high degrees of diversification, Shaw (2023) suggested two types: "related constrained" and "related linked." If the revenue generated by the firm is about 70 percent, it might be considered dominating. More on moderate levels of diversification, Kabeyi (2018) described a related constrained form of diversification as a diversification in which all strategic business units/divisions share product, technology, and distribution channels, and the firm derives about 70 percent of its revenue from the dominant business.

Additionally, firms that get less than 70% of their revenue from their dominating business are considered to have connected linked diversification. There aren't many connections between the strategic business units (Simpson, 2020). Thus, firms with moderate diversification are those that make up about 70% of sales revenue across all businesses, share products, technology, or distribution links, and produce less than 70% of revenue from their core services (Dyer *et al.*, 2016). These happen when there are fewer connections between the new and current business, but the firm's services are still related.

High Level of Diversification

According to Shaw (2023), firms that exhibit unrelated diversification are considered to have a high level of diversification. Less than 70% of its revenue comes from the dominating business, yet the strategic business divisions do not have any connections with one another. When there is no attempt to move resources or operations across firms and the firms compete in product categories and markets with few, if any, links between them, this indicates a high level of diversification (Dyer *et al.*, 2016).

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

The research design used in this study was quantitative, and quantitative data including respondents' background information and the level of diversification of quantity surveying firms in the study areas were all collected through a well-structured questionnaire. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed to analyze the data.

The research population constitutes all the practicing quantity surveying firms in Oyo (25) and in Lagos States (57), and eighty-two (82) in total that were registered with the Quantity Surveying Registration Board of Nigeria (QSRBN) comprised the research population. In each quantity surveying firm, the principal partner or top management personnel or senior quantity surveyors were contacted in Oyo and Lagos States. A census survey was employed for sampling the research population as the population is manageable and advantageous in covering the total population of the research scope as well as attaining accuracy.

This research employed a well-structured questionnaire. Principal partners or senior quantity surveyors at each registered and practicing quantity surveying firm were given the questionnaire in Oyo and Lagos States to ascertain whether the quantity surveying firms have diversified into other businesses outside of their core professional practice and the level at which they diversified, eighty-two (82) questionnaires were distributed. Of the responses, fifty-eight (58) representing 67% of responses were retrieved and found suitable for analysis. Using SPSS 23 software, the gathered data were analyzed using the relevant descriptive statistical methods such as frequency distribution and percentage.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Respondents Background Information

Top management staff; the principal partners, or senior quantity surveyors of quantity surveying firms provided the background information on firms operating in the Oyo and Lagos. The information includes the firm's location, years of establishment, size, and whether or not the firm has expanded into additional businesses. The analysis of responses was presented in Table 1.

Table 1 shows that 64% (37) of the respondents' firms were located in Lagos while the remaining 36% (21) were located in Oyo State. For the year of establishment of the firms, 22% of the firms have been established between 1-5 years, 33% have been established between 6-10 years, 14% have been established between 11-15 years, 9% between 16-20 years and 22% of the respondents' firms have been established for more than 20 years. The distribution size of firms differs as more than half of the respondents' firms have between 1-10 employees (71%), 22% have between 11-49 employees, and 7% have between 50-250 employees.

However, 83% (48) of the respondents affirmed that their firms had diversified into other businesses, while 17% (10) of the firms did not diversify. This implies that the QS firms were established an average of 12 years ago with less than 10 employees, and the majority of the firms diversified to other areas of business.

Table 1: Background Information of Respondents

Information of Respondents	Parameter	Frequency	Percent
Location of firm	Oyo State	21	36.2
	Lagos State	37	63.8
	Total	58	100.0
Years of establishment of firms	1-5 years	13	22.4
	6-10 years	19	32.8
	11-15 years	8	13.8
	16-20 years	5	8.6
	Above 20 years	13	22.4
	Average Years	12	
	Size of Firms (Numbers of employees)	1-10	41
11-49		13	22.4
50-250		4	6.9
Average Employees		19	
Did your firm diversify into other businesses?	Yes	48	82.8
	No	10	17.2
	Total	58	100.0

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Level of Diversification of Quantity Surveying Firms

The result in Table 2 shows that 41% (24) of the QS firms diversified at the moderate level where the firms generated revenue is between 70 percent and 95 percent of income that comes from the dominant business, 17% (10) of the firms were at a high level of diversification; where less than 70 percent of firms generated revenues comes from the dominant business; 24% (14) were at a low level of diversification; where firms generated revenue exceeds 95 percent of the total sales that comes from the core business and 17% (10) of the firms were not diversified. Concerning the different locations, In Lagos state, 10 firms which accounted for 27% of all the QS firms in the state were at a low level of diversification, 14 firms (38%) were at a moderate level of diversification, and only 7 (19%) were at a high level of diversification while 6 (16%) firms did not diversify at all. Meanwhile, for Oyo State, only 4 firms (19%) were at a low level of diversification, 10 firms that accounted for 48% of the total firms in the state were at a moderate level of diversification and just 3 firms that accounted for 14% were at a high level of diversification, while 4 firms that accounted for 19% did not diversify at all. This implies that the majority of the QS firms diversified into other businesses though at a moderate level since it is generated largely from the dominant business.

Table 2: Level of Diversification of Quantity Surveying Firms

Level of diversification	Location of firm		Total
	Oyo State	Lagos State	
Low level of diversification (Firms generated revenue exceeds 95 percent of income that comes from dominant business)	4 19.05%	10 27.02%	14 24.14%
Moderate level of diversification (Firm revenue generated is between 70 percent and 95 percent of income that comes from dominant business)	10 47.61%	14 37.84%	24 41.38%
High level of diversification (Less than 70 percent of revenues generated income comes from dominant business)	3 14.29%	7 18.92%	10 17.24%
Not Diversified	4 19.05%	6 16.22%	10 17.24%
Total	21	37	58

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Discussion of Findings

The findings revealed that the majority of the quantity surveying firms diversified at a moderate level by generating revenue between 70% and 95% from the dominant business. Although this finding may not be in the same order, it is in line with the literature compiled by Adamu *et al.* (2011), where most of the firms studied in Nigeria favored diversifying moderately rather than remaining non-diversified or becoming highly diversified. This was also supported by Adesi *et al.* (2019), who suggested that quantity surveying firms may also adopt diversification as a growth strategy in running their businesses. Also, Simpson (2020) submitted that a company's business is moderate if the generated revenue is between 70 percent and 95 percent from the dominant business. Kabeyi (2018) submitted that a moderate level of diversification is a related constrained form of diversification in which all strategic business units/divisions share product, technology, and distribution channels, and the firm derives about 70 percent of its revenue from the dominant business. Han *et al.* (2019) submitted that the dynamic relationship between the diversification strategy and business performance depends on the diversification level of the company.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This research provides insight into the level of diversification of quantity surveying firms in South West Nigeria; A case study of Oyo and Lagos States, Nigeria. It is evidently to conclude that quantity surveying firms diversified into other construction-related businesses at a moderate level where the firms' generated revenue is about 70% from the dominant business. Based on the findings of this research, for effective diversification of quantity surveying firms into other areas of business to enhance sustainability; it is therefore recommended that quantity surveying firms should embrace diversification into other areas of business at a high level for sustainability in overcoming the turbulence economy in the country.

Contribution to Knowledge

The outcome of this research work has contributed to the body of the academic knowledge and the construction industry at large by establishing the level of diversification of quantity surveying firms in the South West of Nigerian construction industry.

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